

Indantrones from 1-Aminoanthraquinones. Part III. Indanthrone Derivatives : 8-Aminoindanthrone and 8,9-Anthrapyrazoloindanthrone

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Nitration of 1, 2'-dianthrimide yielded 1', 4-dinitro-derivative as indicated by its cleavage with alkaline dithionite which gave quinizarin, and its reduction with hydrazine hydrate and subsequent cyclisation with caustic potash in dimethyl sulphoxide which gave 8, 9-anthrapyrazoloindanthrone. The dinitro compound was reduced to the diamino compound with sodium sulphide. The diamino compound cyclised with caustic potash in dimethyl sulphoxide to 8-aminoindanthrone.

Dinitrodianthrimide was N-methylated. Reduction with hydrazine hydrate gave diamino derivative which did not cyclise with caustic potash in dimethyl sulphoxide.

NITRATION of 1,2'-dianthrimide (1e) with nitric acid in nitrobenzene at 95-100° yields a dinitro compound¹. The positions of nitro groups are stated^{2,3} to be 1'-and 3 or 4 without proof. The structure of the dinitro compound (1f) has now been confirmed by (a) its cleavage with alkaline dithionite which gave quinizarin (III a) and (b) its reduction with hydrazine hydrate to (IV) which cyclised to 8,9-anthrapyrazoloindanthrone (V) with caustic potash in dimethyl sulphoxide. The latter is an interesting addition to the indanthrone family.

The dinitro compound on reduction with methanolic sodium sulphide gave a blue diamino derivative (1c). On reaction with acetic anhydride it gave VI a. 1'-amino-1, 2'-dianthrimide (1a) is stated to react with acetic anhydride to yield VI b⁴. The diamino compound (1c) cyclised to the green 8-aminoindanthrone (IIb) with caustic potash in dimethyl sulphoxide at 60°. It dyed cotton green from blue alkaline dithionite vat which is characteristic of simple indanthrone derivatives. According to a German patent¹, the dinitro compound can be cyclised to aminoindanthrone on fusion with a mixture of sodium sulphide and sodium hydroxide or with sulphur, acetic anhydride and fuming sulphuric acid at 30°.

Despite the existence of many earlier patents, it is doubtful whether the N-methyl derivatives were obtained in a state of purity and whether the N-methyl group remained intact under the conditions of cyclisation before the work of Bradley *et. al.*⁵. Condensation of 1-methylamino-2-bromo-anthraquinone with 1-aminoanthraquinone and subsequent cyclisation cannot yield a pure product as the N-alkyl group would be eliminated as formaldehyde in the first step.^{6,7} Condensation of *o*-amino-1,2'-dianthrimides substituted on the nitrogen atom by the alkyl group under vigorous conditions using manganese dioxide, potassium permanganate, nitric acid or oxygen in sulphuric acid can scarcely be expected to yield N-alkyl indantrones⁸.

In the present work, dinitrodianthrimide was N-alkylated by methyl-*p*-toluene sulphonate in *o*-dichlorobenzene. The N-methyl compound (1g) however was more susceptible to cleavage by alkaline reducing agents. Most of it cleaved with aqueous alcoholic sodium sulphide. A major product isolated was 1-amino-4-hydroxy-anthraquinone (III b). After removal of acetone solubles, the remaining product analysed for N-methylated amino nitrodianthrimide. It did not cyclise to an indanthrone derivative with caustic potash in dimethyl sulphoxide.

Reduction with stannous chloride in acetic acid gave a yellow brown product which did not analyse for the diamine.

Reduction with hydrazine hydrate also brought about the cleavage but a small amount of the diamino compound (1d) was obtained. The product reacted with acetic anhydride to yield the diacetylamino derivative (1h). The properties of the diamino-compound (1d) differed from those of the nonalkylated diamine (1c). Cyclisation of this compound (1d) with caustic potash in dimethyl sulphoxide however did not take place as indicated by its dyeing properties.

The failure of N-methyl compounds (1b and 1d) to cyclise is interesting as Bradley⁵ has obtained 6-methyl- and 6,15-dimethyl-indantrones on cyclisation of (1i) and (1j) respectively on treatment with pyridine and caustic potash.

Experimental

1',4-Dinitro-1,2'-dianthrimide (1f): Nitric acid (2 ml., *d*=1.5) was added in an hour to a suspension of 1, 2'-dianthrimide (3 g.) in nitrobenzene (20 ml.) at 95°-100°. The mixture was stirred for another hour at that temperature and allowed to cool. Orange needles which separated were collected, washed with benzene

and dried. Crystallisation from nitrobenzene gave orange needles (1.5 g.) (Found : C, 64.9 ; H, 2.3 ; N, 7.8. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{13}N_3O_8$. C, 64.7 ; H, 2.5 ; N, 8.1 percent.) The dinitro compound dissolved in conc. sulphuric acid with violet colour. Its orange red solution in pyridine turned green on addition of methanolic caustic potash.

Reduction with alkaline dithionite : A solution of sodium hydroxide (4 g.) and sodium dithionite (9 g.) in water (100 ml.) at 65° was added to a paste of finely divided nitro compound (1.4 g.) in alcohol (10 ml.). The mixture was heated to boiling for 30 min. An orange red solution formed which turned blue and a blue precipitate separated. It was collected. Crystallisation from aniline gave blue needles of diamindianthrimide. Its properties and analysis are described in a later experiment.

The filtrate was acidified with hydrochloric acid and the precipitate filtered. Its solution in benzene was chromatographed on silica gel. It separated into two fractions : (1) a strongly adsorbed black fraction and (2) a weakly adsorbed red fraction. The latter was eluted with pure benzene. Crystallisation from benzene gave red needles of quinizarin, m.p. and mixed m. p. with quinizarin, 198° (m.p. in lit.⁹, 197°-8°).

1'-Amino-4, 10-anthrapyrazolo-1, 2'-dianthrimide (IV) : 1',4-Dinitro-1,2'-dianthrimide (1 g.) was added to pyridine (20 ml.) followed by hydrazine hydrate (1 ml. of 99-100%). The orange solution changed to blue on addition of hydrazine hydrate. The mixture was refluxed for 5 hr and then diluted with water and the precipitate collected. Crystallisation from *o*-dichlorobenzene gave blue microplates (0.7 g.) (Found ; C, 73.6 ; H, 3.1 ; N, 11.9. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{16}N_4O_8$, C, 73.7 ; H, 3.5 ; N, 12.3%). It dissolved in conc. sulphuric acid with violet colour. It dissolved in alkaline dithionite solution to give an orange vat which had no affinity for cotton.

8,9-Anthrapyrazoloindanthrone (V) : A mixture of the above compound (1 g.), DMSO (10 ml), and potassium hydroxide (2 g.) was stirred at 70° for 4 hr. The product was collected after diluting it with water. The residue on crystallisation from aniline gave bluish green plates (0.6 g.) (Found : C, 74.1 ; H, 3.0 ; N, 12.2. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{14}N_4O_8$, C, 74.0 ; H, 3.1 ; N, 12.3%). It dissolved in conc. sulphuric acid with olive green colour. Its bluish green solution in pyridine turned maroon on addition of methanolic caustic potash. It dyed cotton bluish green from bluish gray alkaline dithionite vat.

1',4-Diamino-1, 2'-dianthrimide (Ic) : A mixture of 1',4 dinitro-1,2'-dianthrimide (2 g.), sodium sulphide (2 g.), water (8 ml.) and methanol (32 ml) was refluxed with stirring for 4 hr. A reddish blue solution of the diamine was produced on heating. The blue compound (1.8 g.) was collected after dilution with water. Crystallisation from aniline gave blue needles. (Found ; C, 72.9 ; H, 3.4 ; N, 8.9%. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{17}N_5O_4$, C, 73.2 ; H, 3.7 ; N, 9.1%. It dissolved in conc. sulphuric acid

with blue colour. It dissolved in alkaline dithionite with orange red vat with no affinity for cotton.

Acetylation of 1',4-diamino-1,2'-dianthrimide : The above compound (1 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (20 ml.) for 6 hr. Dilution of the solution with aqueous alcohol gave a blue product which crystallised from *o*-dichlorobenzene in blue plates. It analysed corresponding to the formula (VI a). (Found ; C, 73.3 ; H, 3.6 ; N, 7.6. Calcd. for $C_{32}H_{19}N_5O_5$, C, 73.1 ; H, 3.6 ; N, 7.9%.

I

II a, R=H

b, R=NH₂

- a, (R = R₁ = R₂ = H, R₃ = NH₂)
- b, (R = CH₃, R₁ = R₂ = H, R₃ = NH₂)
- c, (R = R₁ = H, R₂ = R₃ = NH₂)
- d, (R = CH₃, R₁ = R₂ = NH₂, R₃ = H)
- e, (R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = R = H)
- f, (R = R₁ = H, R₂ = R₃ = NO₂)
- g, (R = CH₃, R₁ = R₂ = NO₂, R₃ = H)
- h, (R = CH₃, R₁ = R₂ = NHCOCH₃, R₃ = H)
- i, (R₃ = NH₂, R = CH₃, R₁ = R₂ = H)
- j, (R₃ = NHCH₃, R = CH₃, R₁ = R₂ = H)

8-Aminoindanthrone (II b.) A mixture of 1',4-diamino-1,2'-dianthrimide (1 g.), DMSO (10 ml.), and caustic potash (2 g.) was stirred at 70° for 6 hr. The product (0.5 g.) was collected after dilution with water. Crystallisation from nitrobenzene gave green needles. (Found ; C, 73.2 ; H, 3.2 ; N, 9.0. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{15}N_3O_8$, C, 73.5 ; H, 3.3 ; N, 9.2%. It dissolved in conc. sulphuric acid with olive green colour. Its green pyridine solution turned light brown on addition of methanolic caustic potash. It dyed cotton green from blue alkaline dithionite vat.

III a, (R₁ = R₂ = OH)

b, (R₁ = NH₂, R₂ = OH)

IV

1',4 - Dinitro-N-methyl - 1,2' - dianthrimide (Ig) : 1',4-Dinitro-1,2'-dianthrimide (5g.), methyl *p*-toluene sulphonate (5g.) and dry potassium carbonate (4g.) were heated in *o*-dichlorobenzene (20ml.) for 9 hr at reflux. The suspension was cooled and filtered. The residue was washed with hot solvent and the washing and filtrate were combined and concentrated to small volume. On cooling, an orange precipitate (4 g.) was obtained. Crystallisation from *o*-dichlorobenzene gave orange red needles. (Found ; C, 65.3 ; H, 2.8 ; N, 7.6. Calcd. for $C_{29}H_{15}N_3O_8$, C, 65.3 ; H, 2.8 ; N, 7.9%). It dissolved in conc. sulphuric acid with violet colour.

Reduction of (Ig)

(a) A mixture of the above compound (2 g.), sodium sulphide (2 g.) water (8ml.), and methanol (32ml.) was

refluxed with stirring for 4 hrs. A bluish red product separated on dilution of the reaction mixture with water. It was Soxhlet-extracted with methanol. The methanol solubles were dissolved in benzene and chromatographed on silica gel. The weakly adsorbed major blue band, on concentration gave reddish violet plates of 1-amino-4-hydroxy-anthraquinone, m. p. and m. m.p. 207° (Found ; C, 70.0 ; H, 3.6 ; N, 5.6. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_9NO_3$, C, 70.3 ; H, 3.8 ; N, 5.9%) m.p. and m. m. p. of its diacetyl derivative, 194°.

The insoluble residue (0.3 g.) crystallised from aniline in bluish green needles and analysed for aminonitro-N-methyl-dianthrimide. (Found ; C, 69.3 ; H, 3.3 ; N, 8.0%. Calcd. for $C_{29}H_{17}N_3O_8$, C, 69.1 ; H, 3.4 ; N, 8.3%. It dissolved in conc. sulphuric acid with greenish gray colour, and in alkaline dithionite to reddish brown vat. It did not cyclise to an indanthrone derivative with caustic potash in DMSO at 60°.

(b) Dinitro-N-methyl-dianthrimide (2 g.) was added to a boiling solution containing stannous chloride (8 g.) in acetic acid (40ml). After 10 min., the solution was cooled and mixed with water. A yellow brown precipitate (2 g.) was collected. Crystallisation from DMF gave yellowish brown plates. (Found ; C, 75.8 ; H, 4.4 ; N, 4.5%). It dissolved in conc. sulphuric acid with orange yellow colour.

(c) Dinitro-N-methyl-dianthrimide (1 g.) was added to pyridine (20ml.) followed by hydrazine hydrate (1ml. of 99-100%). The solution was refluxed for 5 hr. It

was diluted with water and the precipitate was collected. Acetone solubles were removed by Soxhlet-extraction. The insoluble residue (0.2 g.) crystallised from aniline in blue plates and analysed for the diamine. (Found ; C, 73.8 ; H, 4.0 ; N, 8.8. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{18}N_3O_4$, C, 73.6 ; H, 4.0 ; N, 8.9%). It dissolved in conc. sulphuric acid with yellowish brown colour and in alkaline dithionite with reddish brown vat which had no affinity for cotton.

It did not yield an indanthrone derivative when reacted with caustic potash in DMSO at 60° for 6 hr.

1',4-Diacetylamino-N-methyl-1,2'-dianthrimide(Ih)

The above diamino compound (0.4 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (10ml.) for 6 hr. Dilution of the solution with aqueous alcohol gave a blue product which crystallised from aniline in blue needles. (Found ; C, 70.9 ; H, 4.3 ; N, 7.8. Calcd. for $C_{38}H_{28}N_3O_6$, C, 71.1 ; H, 4.2 ; N, 7.5%)

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